

Misconduct and plagiarism related to the grant proposal

Background:

Supervisor B asked the PhD candidate A to draft a grant proposal for him. Since A did not have much relevant experience, she purchased the tutoring services of a tutoring agency which is helping to write grant proposal. When A wrote the grant proposal, she plagiarized many contents of the "case samples" provided by the tutoring agency. After this grant proposal was submitted in the name of supervisor B, it was reviewed by the fund agency and determined to be plagiarism. Supervisor B's application qualification was cancelled, and he was publicly criticized.

C discovered that 'the successful case samples' that were used by the tutoring agency to make profits were exactly the same one he had written before with other tree co-authors D, E and F. Three years ago, the four of them worked together as a research team, shared a similar literature review and methodology. All four of them applied for funds, and as separate grant proposals, they all belonged to a complex problem researched by a team. However, C's grant proposal was not approved three times and was the one that was plagiarized heavily by A.

(197 words)

Questions for the original authors C, D, E, F:

- The four of them worked together as a research team, shared a similar literature review and methodology. They were involved in plagiarism from each other.
- For author A, is it misconduct to submit the same or similar grant proposal three times?
- How were the grant proposal be stolen? What are the possible specific issues when it comes to data management security?

Questions for supervisor B and the PhD candidate A:

- For supervisor B, asking someone else to write for he/she is misconduct.
- Was candidate A under the pressure of her supervisor? Is it in line with the 'Golden Rules for PhD Supervision'?

Questions for the tutoring agency:

- How did they get this grant proposal? What are the possible specific issues when it comes to data management security?
- Is it illegal to sell someone's disapproved grant proposal and lie that it's a successful case for profits?

Questions for the fund agency:

- What are the criteria to determine the reuse or similar to earlier submitted grant proposals? And how to deal with this misconduct?